

Father's Involvement in Providing Complementary Foods to Toddlers 6-24 Months in An Effort to Reduce Stunting in Bandung City-Indonesia

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ABSTRACT: Parenting applied by parents will affect the growth and development of toddlers because malnutrition during toddlerhood will be irreversible (cannot recover), so at this time, toddlers need quality food intake. The better the parenting style, the better the nutritional status. Good parenting is reflected in the better food intake given to toddlers. This type of research is descriptive qualitative analytics (exploratory study) using a cross-sectional design which is an analytical study to analyze the effect of fathers' involvement in providing complementary foods with the incidence of stunting. The research was conducted in Bandung City, West Java Province. The population in this study was mothers who had toddlers aged 6-24 months. The sample in this study is fathers who have 102 toddlers living in Bandung City in 2022 using the proportional random sampling formula. In this study, the P-value was 0.291, which means there is no significant relationship between the involvement of fathers in providing complementary foods with the incidence of stunting in Bandung. Risk factors for stunting in toddlers are education level, local food processing, parental knowledge, health role power, and husband support. The factor most associated with stunting is paternal involvement.

KEYWORDS: Father's involvement, complementary foods, toddlers, stunting

1. INTRODUCTION

Stunting is caused by multidimensional factors, namely poor parenting during the First 1000 Days of Life (HPK) of children due to lack of knowledge about health and nutrition before and during pregnancy, not getting exclusive breastfeeding for children 0-24 months old, not receiving complementary foods (MP ASI), limited health services (including Ante Natal Care services, Post-Christmas and quality early learning), lack of access to nutritious food. Improving people's nutritional status is the second indicator of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), both of which are realized by efforts to end hunger, achieve food security and good nutrition, and improve sustainable agriculture. Parenting applied by parents will affect the growth and development of toddlers because malnutrition during toddlerhood will be irreversible (cannot recover), so at this time, toddlers need quality food intake. This is reinforced by research conducted in East Nusa Tenggara-Indonesia that the parenting style applied by mothers will determine the nutritional status of toddlers (1). The better the parenting style, the better the nutritional status. Good parenting is reflected in the better food intake given to toddlers.

In 2030, it is hoped that these efforts will succeed in solving various nutrition-related problems by utilizing food inadequacy by eliminating all forms of hunger or malnutrition and ensuring access for everyone, especially the poor and people who are in vulnerable conditions to nutritious, nutritious, and sufficient food (2). A total of 10 (ten) villages spread across 8 (eight) districts in Bandung Regency are priorities for handling stunting, because the prevalence is quite high. Each of them is Rancafurnace Village (Pameungpeuk), Dampit, Narawita and Tanjungwangi (Cicalengka), Mekarlaksana (Cikancung), Babakan (Ciparay), Girimulya (Package), Cihawuk (Kertasari), Karangtunggal (Paseh) and Cibodas Village (Kec. Pasirjambu sub-district), (3). Indonesia is included in the third country with the highest prevalence in Southeast Asia (SEAR). The average prevalence of stunting toddlers in Indonesia in 2005-2017 was 36.4%. 3 more than a third (37%) of children under five in Indonesia were stunted in 2013 and the prevalence exceeded 40% in 15 out of 33 provinces. WHO targets a reduction in stunting rates in children not enough from 5 years, namely 40% by 2025. In 2018, East Nusa Tenggara was 42.6%, West Sulawesi was 42% and Aceh was 35%. The prevalence of stunting in West Java is 29.2% or 2.7 million children under five. The incidence of stunting in Indonesia is quite high when compared to middle-income countries. The incidence of stunting according to Basic Health Research in 2018 (4) was 10.2% while the prevalence of stunting in children under five was 30.8% (4). The number of children under five suffering from stunting (failure to thrive) in Bandung City has increased in 2020. From data from the Bandung City Health Office, the number of stunted toddlers reached 9,567 or 8.93 percent of the 107,189 toddlers measured (2).

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2. METHOD

This type of research is descriptive qualitative analytics (exploratory study) using a cross-sectional design which is an analytical study to analyze the effect of fathers' involvement in providing complementary foods with the incidence of stunting. The research was conducted in Bandung City, West Java Province. The population in this study was mothers who had toddlers aged 6-24 months. The sample in this study is fathers who have 102 toddlers living in Bandung City in 2022 using the proportional random sampling formula, which determines the number of respondents in the community health center area. The sampling technique used is non-probability using Purposive Sampling where this method uses criteria that have been selected by researchers in choosing a sample. In this study, the variable studied was the involvement of fathers in providing complementary foods to toddlers. The chi-square correlation test is used to analyze the relationship between independent and dependent variables. The sample used in this study was fathers who had babies aged 6 months to 24 months.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

a. Frequency distribution of nutritional status of toddlers and involvement of fathers in providing complementary foods

Figure 1. Distribution of nutritional status of toddlers aged 6-24 months

In the distribution of nutritional status of toddlers above, it was found that toddlers who experienced stunting nutrition were 63 toddlers with a percentage value of 61.8%. While toddlers who have normal nutritional status as many as 39 with a percentage of 38.2%. In this study, researchers deliberately chose toddlers with the most stunting nutritional status. Because researchers want to see the efforts and involvement of fathers in providing nutritional intake to toddlers.

Figure 2. Frequency of father's involvement in providing complementary foods to toddlers

Gabar 2 above explains the frequency of fathers' involvement in providing complementary foods where it was found that fathers who were not involved in providing complementary foods were 66 respondents with a percentage of 64.7%. While fathers involved in providing foreign complementary foods as many as 36 respondents with a percentage of 35.3%. This proves that father always does not take part in the interests of nutritional intake, father spends his time working and being outside the home.

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b. The relationship between fathers' involvement in providing complementary foods to toddlers with the incidence of stunting

Table 1. Risk Factors for Stunting in Toddlers

Factor	Nutritional Status				Total		P-Value	OR (95% CI)
	Stunting		Normal					
	n	%	n	%	n	%		
Father's involvement								
Not Involved	39	61.9	27	38	63	100	0.291	0,722
Involved	27	69.2	12	30.8	39	100		

Fathers were not involved in complementary feeding of stunted toddlers with a proportion of 61.9%, while fathers who supported the provision of nutritional intake in toddlers had normal nutritional status of 69%. In this study, the P-value was 0.291, which means there is no significant relationship between the involvement of fathers in providing complementary foods with the incidence of stunting in Bandung. According to Effendy 2009, family support is an attitude or act of family acceptance towards family members, in the form of informational support, assessment support, instrumental support, and emotional support. According to him, family support is very important because the family is the smallest unit in society so that nursing care is accepted. Therefore, it is the family that plays a role in determining the treatment methods needed by sick family members, if in that family one of the family members has health problems, the system in the family will be affected (5). So family support is a form of interpersonal relationship that includes attitudes, actions and acceptance towards family members, so that family members feel cared for (6). This illustrates that father's behavior in loving toddlers. Good enough even though dad rarely takes care of his toddler because dad is busy working. The role carried by the father is no less important than the role of a ibu_pengasuhan and parenting at home because the role of the father is also important in shaping the growth and emotional development of children in children. If a father gives full love to the child then the child will feel happy and comfortable when around his father and better if a father does not give attention and affection to his child, then the child will feel sad and uncomfortable when with his father. Father's attitude does not affect the nutritional status of toddlers because there is the most important factor that affects the nutritional status of toddlers, namely food with good nutrition. Foods with various nutritional contents are needed by toddlers for growth and development. Toddlers will grow optimally if their food intake is in sufficient quantities, nutritious, and balanced (7). Parental attitudes, especially health behaviors such as nutritional fulfillment in children, can cause misperceptions and parenting patterns in toddlers. In learning, this attitude is the attitude of parents in the form of evaluation of the nutritional status of toddlers, how to provide food for toddlers, the growth of toddlers (3) explained that there is a relationship between community attitudes and the incidence of stunting in toddlers. Parenting patterns will indirectly affect the nutritional status of children. Childcare is manifested in several activities that are usually carried out by mothers such as child feeding practices, sanitation practices and child health care in order to have a major impact on children's health in the future. Feeding that does not pay attention to the frequency of administration, nutritional quality and improper feeding methods will also result in growth failure.

This proves the existence of a relationship between knowledge and attitude, a positive attitude is influenced by good knowledge. This study is in line with research conducted by (Harikatan et (8). In his research it was said that more than half of the respondents had a positive attitude, namely 34 respondents (57.6%). The attitude that mothers have is positive It is inseparable from the knowledge or information obtained, and the knowledge possessed by good mothers or in high categories so that it is in the form of a positive attitude or good mother's assessment of stunting events. According to Rahmayanti, (9) Attitude is a closed reaction or response of a person to a stimulus or object, where the attitude basically cannot be directly seen, but can only be interpreted in advance from closed behavior. Attitude is not yet an action or activity, but forms the predisposition of action of a behavior and is a driver of one's behavior to act But a positive attitude alone without the support of other factors certainly guarantees someone to do something. The role of the father in the family Not only that it affects changes in the socioeconomic status of the family and is closely related to involvement in parenting. Fathers' involvement in parenting includes aspects of time, interaction, and attention to children. Father's involvement in parenting Not only is the quantity of time more for the child, but the quality of interaction that is built is also fundamental. The role of a father in toddlers is no less important than a mother in fulfilling nutrition. Dad also worked to manage and control family expenses. Father's involvement in parenting is the father's continuous participation in parenting a pregnant child from the aspects of frequency, initiative, and personal empowerment in physical, emotional, social, intellectual, and moral dimensions. This research is in line with research conducted by (10) which states that the test results show that the involvement of fathers in parenting has a significant positive effect on the cognitive development of children aged 2-3 years in the field of stunting prevalence. Findings that are in line with previous research have also found that fathers' involvement in parenting has a significant effect on children's cognitive (11). The role of fathers will influence the development of social skills, cognitive development, and emotional (Lolan and sutriawan, 2023) (12). To realize attitudes in providing nutritious food into a real action, supporting factors

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or something that is possible, among others, are facilities. Father's attitude that will have an impact on father's involvement in feeding children, A study in Ethiopia showed that fathers who have good participation in child feeding activities have a positive influence on better dietary diversity (12)

4. CONCLUSION

Risk factors for stunting in toddlers are education level, local food processing, parental knowledge, health role power, husband support. The factor most associated with stunting is paternal involvement. Father's involvement is one of the most influential factors on the incidence of stunting, this is because the role of fathers in the family is not solely to seek or improve the economy, but besides that fathers have an important role in parenting. Fathers' involvement in parenting which includes aspects of time, interaction, and attention to children can have a significant positive effect on the cognitive development of children aged 2-3 years in the field of stunting prevalence.

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